

Milestone MS8

Workshop across the EOV projects (sister projects)

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MILESTONE

Milestone	MS8 Workshop across EOVS projects (sister projects)
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1. What is this milestone about

This milestone comprises a report on a workshop that responds to the growing international momentum to evolve Essential Ocean Variables-based approaches into actionable ocean indicators that support policy, governance, and operational decision-making. Held on 2 July 2025, this **workshop on Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) projects** brought together the ObsSea4Clim and BioEcoOcean sister projects, funded under the Horizon Europe programme, to foster synergies across ocean observing disciplines and discuss project outcomes with the GOOS initiative on ocean indicators. By uniting expertise from these projects, the workshop aimed to drive progress toward a more comprehensive, cost-effective, and coordinated approach to ocean monitoring and sustainable management.

2. Milestone report

2.1 Means of verification

The means to verify that this milestone has been achieved is as follows: documentation, materials, and reports are available to the partners.

2.2 Work performed

2.2.1 Background and objectives of the workshop

The global community is increasingly recognising the critical role of **EOVs** in supporting science-based policies for ocean health, climate action, and sustainable development. Measuring EOVS crucial for delivering accurate ocean forecasts, climate projections, and assessments of ecosystem health. By connecting physical, biogeochemical, and biological processes across Earth systems - including the atmosphere, biosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere, and human dimensions - EOVS provide a core foundation for sustained, interdisciplinary ocean observations.

While progress has been made in defining and standardising EOVS through the **Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)**, there is **no internationally agreed-upon**

framework for ocean indicators to monitor physical, biogeochemical, biological and ecosystem processes. To address this, GOOS launched an [initiative in 2021](#) to develop a global Ocean Indicator Framework, in collaboration with GEO BluePlanet, the OceanObs'19 Living Action Plan, the G7 Future of the Sea, and the UN Ocean Decade of Science. This workshop aims to align and support the work carried out by EOVS projects on physics, biochemistry and biodiversity in relation to ocean indicators with the GOOS Ocean Indicators Framework.

This workshop responds to the growing international momentum to evolve EOVS-based approaches into actionable ocean indicators that serve policy, governance, and operational decision-making. By uniting expertise from these projects, the workshop aims to drive progress toward a more comprehensive, cost-effective, and coordinated approach to ocean monitoring and sustainable management.

The workshop aimed at:

- **Sharing status on the indicators work and next steps** within the projects' timelines.
- **Opportunities for collaboration and cross-project synergies**, guidance and best practices.
- **Discussion on how to best contribute to GOOS** initiative on ocean indicators.

Workshop across EOVS projects to foster synergies in our work on:

- Essential Ocean Variables
- Ocean indicators
- Best practices
- Observational requirements

2.2.2 Format and materials

The workshop was held online for two hours on July 2, 2025. Given the internal nature of this cross-cutting meeting, the workshop attracted the participation of representatives from the organising partner and the represented projects.

The workshop's detailed agenda is presented below, highlighting the topics discussed.

Agenda

Welcome and Introduction by EuroGOOS

ObsSea4Clim - Progress and updates by Project partners

- Short project overview and introduction to the work packages' roles.
- ObsSea4Clim Indicator framework (WP3): EOVS-based ocean indicators for climate. An update on the work done so far in this specific work package..
- The Concept of the preliminary Design of a Federated Network for Methodologies in Ocean Observing: The concept of this federated network is provided in the ObsSea4Clim milestone [MS17](#) "Preliminary Design of a Federated Network for Methodologies in Ocean Observing". The presentation also covered the introduction to the related [survey](#) organised by IEEE France
- The Questionnaire about Requirements: A [survey](#) designed to standardise and streamline the collection and formalisation of observational requirements

BioEcoOcean - Progress and updates by Project Coordinator

- A short project overview and WP3 *Filling the knowledge gaps for observing BioEco services - research on EOVS* and WP4 *Blueprint Application & Testing: Demonstrating an operational workflow for BioEco EOVS development*.
- Filling the knowledge gaps for observing BioEco services - research on EOVS, including key variables and FAIR data.

Discussion - All participants

Wrapping up – next steps by EuroGOOS and Projects Coordinators

- Specific actions and timeline.
- How will the outcomes of this discussion be fed back to GOOS?
- Follow-up mechanisms, such as joint sessions, workshops, and shared repositories.

Speaker	Organisation	Project affiliation
Steffen M. Olsen	Danish Meteorological Institute	Coordinator, ObsSea4Clim
Karina von Schuckmann	Mercator Ocean International	ObsSea4Clim
Jay Pearlman	IEEE France	ObsSea4Clim
Sabrina Speich	Ecole Normale Supérieure- Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique	ObsSea4Clim
Alessandra Onida	Ecole Normale Supérieure- Laboratoire	ObsSea4Clim

	de Météorologie Dynamique	
Lina Mtwana Nordlund	Uppsala University	Coordinator, BioEcoOcean
Nina Lepola	Uppsala University	BioEcoOcean
Manuel Sala Perez	EuroGOOS	ObsSea4Clim

Table 1: Keynote speakers and their organisational and project affiliations.

2.2.3 Summary of discussion

Welcome and Introduction

The workshop was opened by the EuroGOOS moderator, who welcomed all participants. Participants were asked to introduce themselves briefly. The moderator introduced the agenda, the context and the objectives of the workshop.

ObsSea4Clim - Progress and updates

1. *Project overview and introduction on the work packages' roles - Steffen M. Olsen (Danish Meteorological Institute)*

The presentation summarised the focus of the ObsSea4Clim project on enhancing the role of ocean observations in climate assessments by advancing the use of EOVS and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs). The project aims to develop interoperable data ecosystems and establish best practices ([WP2](#)) for both in situ and satellite observations. A key component is the regionalisation and refinement of ocean indicators, including those related to marine extremes such as heatwaves and sea level anomalies ([WP3](#)). ObsSea4Clim supports the improvement of Earth System Models, contributing to more accurate climate projections. Through stakeholder co-design and multidisciplinary collaboration, the initiative seeks to make ocean science more actionable and to position Europe as a global leader in ocean-climate coordination.

2. *Concept of the preliminary Design of a Federated Network for Methodologies in Ocean Observing (Milestone MS17) - Jay Pearlman (IEEE France)*

The presentation introduced the Ocean Practices Federated Network (OPFN), a global initiative designed to connect fragmented Methodology Management Systems (MMS) across the ocean science community. The OPFN network enables centralised discovery

and distributed access to ocean methods, best practices, and standards. Initially motivated by aquaculture users, OPFN now serves a broader community by supporting interoperability, autonomy, and adaptability across diverse systems. A conceptual architecture has been developed as a beta version of the OPFN user interface, along with a comprehensive survey of forty-eight repositories for oceanographic data and methods. The interface allows users to select methods based on subject, Essential Ocean Variables, maturity, endorsement status, and language. Efforts are also underway to link best practices to data and information holdings, thereby improving discoverability and usability.

OPFN is actively seeking collaboration with BioEcoOcean project partners to identify relevant repositories and define key subject areas for pilot integration. Partners are encouraged to participate in beta testing of the OPFN interface and contribute to the development of harmonised method selection tools. Future actions include iterative planning and development to ensure the network evolves in alignment with user needs and scientific priorities. It was agreed that the survey would be shared among BioEcoOcean partners and collaborators. In addition, it was highlighted that the biodiversity observation community may utilise alternative databases other than marine-related repositories, e.g., the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), which would also need to be explored. It was confirmed that expansion is planned in the next step of the work.

3. EOv-based ocean indicators for climate / Update on the work done so far in WP3 - Karina von Schuckmann (Mercator Ocean International)

Work Package 3 of the ObsSea4Clim project focuses on developing and refining ocean indicators based on Essential Ocean Variables to support climate assessments, policy-making, and stakeholder engagement. The work is structured into three main tasks, each contributing to the broader goal of creating actionable, regionally relevant climate indicators.

Task 3.1 – Regionalisation of Ocean Indicators

This task focuses on identifying and refining indicators for key EOvs such as sea surface temperature (SST), sea surface height (SSH), sea ice, and subsurface temperature. A regional approach has been adopted to capture unique patterns and trends, isolate local drivers, and support policy development. Indicators under development include sea ice extent, thickness, drift, and SST-based metrics like freezing degree days and melt days. Case studies, such as mussel population declines in Ireland and Spain, are being used to link biological impacts with regional SST trends.

Task 3.2 – Marine Extremes and Heatwaves

The team has made significant progress in defining indicators for marine heatwaves (MHWs), emphasising the need for flexible, context-specific approaches. A new global dataset of MHWs (1982–2024) has been created using the OSTIA SST product, incorporating multiple climatologies, thresholds, and definitions. This dataset supports sensitivity analyses and enables users to build custom indicators. Activities include an MHW hackathon, studies on the deep impacts of MHW, and ongoing research into MHW drivers and methodological robustness.

Task 3.3 – Support to GOOS and Ocean Narratives

Task 3.3 contributes to the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) indicator framework by developing ocean narratives and exploring compound effects. Collaborative publications are underway, and conceptual work is progressing on harmonised indicator messaging and digital platform integration.

WP3 is actively fostering collaboration through test beds for regional indicators, joint impact studies, and harmonisation of methods. These efforts aim to advance the GOOS pilot indicators and support the development of a digital platform for disseminating these indicators. Ideas for collaboration were discussed with the workshop participants, including regionalisation indicators, harmonisation methods, and reporting methods.

Additionally, the involvement of stakeholders in co-developing the Ocean Indicators was discussed. It was clarified that, as part of the work in WP3, there have been and will be opportunities for end users to collaborate on the indicators work. In relation to biodiversity indicators, it was highlighted that changes in biodiversity occur at the local scale; therefore, a finer scale of forecasting, e.g., heat waves, would be necessary to address the impact of these events on biodiversity. It was agreed to explore this together among the partners of the sister projects. Likewise, it was noted that the relevance of more explicitly linking ocean indicators to SDG 14.

4. *Questionnaire about Requirements - Designed to standardise and streamline the collection and formalisation of observational requirements - Alessandra Onida (Ecole Normale Supérieure - Laboratoire de Météorologie).*

This presentation outlined the development and purpose of the Requirements Questionnaire, a tool designed to support the Rolling Review of Requirements (RRR) in ocean-related Application Areas. The work is part of Task 2.1 within ObsSea4Clim and is conducted in collaboration with WMO, GOOS, and ESACs. **The Application Areas in ObsSea4Clim are treated as Sub-Application Areas under the broader WMO Climate Application Area framework.** The main objective is to develop a structured, evidence-based process for defining observational requirements. The Requirements Questionnaire serves as a standardised format for stakeholders to define and assess observational needs within each Application Area. It is aligned with the frameworks and guidance provided by GOOS and WMO.

The questionnaire is structured as follows:

1. Definition of the Sub-Application Area (Sub-AA): Users select the definition of the Application Area, which guides the formulation of requirements.
2. Extent of Observations: Horizontal, vertical, and temporal extents are specified using three levels: Ideal, Desirable, and Minimum.
3. Table of Requirements: Includes relevance of EOVS, observational resolution (horizontal, vertical, temporal), timeliness, uncertainty, stability per decade, and best practices for observing methods.

As a part of the upcoming activities, ObsSea4Clim WP4 will join a kick-off meeting with WP2 to present and explain the questionnaire. Additionally, follow-up meetings with each Application Area group will be conducted to collaboratively complete the questionnaire and gather feedback from the users.

BioEcoOcean - Progress and updates

Project coordinator Lina Mtwana Nordlund provided an overview of the BioEcoOcean project, emphasising that it operates through a network of Living Labs and structured Work Packages to enhance BioEco EOVS through collaborative research, updated specifications, and integration into decision-making frameworks. BioEcoOcean aims to bridge the maturity gap between biological/ecosystem Essential Ocean Variables and their physical counterparts.

The project has achieved and produced important milestones and outcomes, such as:

- Deliverable 2.1: Guide to EOVS specification sheets.
- Deliverable 2.3: Updated specification sheets aligned with GOOS standards.
- Establishment of Coastal and Pelagic Living Labs focusing on macroalgae, seagrass, fish, phyto- zooplankton and sea turtles.
- Use of high-resolution remote sensing to support coastal EOVS development.
- Creation of the Marine Organic Carbon Atlas (MOCA) to map carbon stocks and fluxes, with a pilot in the Arctic.
- As a part of the work carried out in WP3 and WP4, validate technologies, assess biodiversity change, and enhance early warning systems.

BioEcoOcean foresees a number of opportunities for collaboration across sister projects, such as:

- Simultaneous collection of Biodiversity and Physical EOVS to streamline data pipelines and improve integration of biological and physical EOVS.

- Joint visualisation and analysis of biological and physical EOVS to understand their interactions and how physical and chemical drivers affect biodiversity changes.
- Research collaboration to investigate the impact of physical EOVS on marine biodiversity and ecosystem dynamics, particularly in local coastal environments.
- Work towards alignment with ObsSea4Clim Task 4.5 to develop Early Warning Systems and forecasting tools, including biological EOVS and Ecosystem dynamics.

BioEcoOcean will continue to refine EOVS specification sheets and integrate socio-economic variables, while also expanding the use of remote sensing and forecasting tools across Living Labs. BioEcoOcean aims to foster stakeholder engagement and lead co-creation events on indicators with key stakeholders. In addition, BioEcoOcean aims to strengthen its collaboration with sister projects and global initiatives in the following months to ensure sustained EU leadership in ocean-climate-biodiversity science.

Partners from ObsSea4Clim acknowledged the potential opportunities for collaboration. In addition, a representative from the BioGeoSea project emphasised that partners from all sister projects would be welcome to join the BioGeoSea Kick-off meeting from September 29th to October 1st, 2025. It was noted that a session dedicated to following up on the work carried out during the 1st Cluster Event (D6.1) could be organised as a part of the Kick-off meeting.

Next Steps

The presentations and the following discussion highlighted the strong potential for synergies across the sister projects. It was agreed to work together via bilateral meetings, ad-hoc working groups, EOVS Forum and workshops on a set of topics after the summer break, depending on availability, such as:

- Integrate physical EOVS into biodiversity changes, e.g., marine heatwaves.
- Work on the Early Warning System across sister projects
- It was noted that the example of the Hackathon on marine heat waves could be replicated for other synergetic topics, such as Living Labs or Ocean Narrative.
- User requirements, data products and requirements for indicators, since these issues are common ground across the three sister projects
- Working group to draft collaboratively white papers and publications
- Stakeholder involvement and co-design of Ocean indicators
- Piloting ocean indicators across sister projects using feedback and input from cross-cutting stakeholders (key stakeholders identified across the three projects)

3. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

This milestone contributes to achieving the following specific objectives of the project.

#SO1	<p>To develop ocean indicators, provide improved EOv/ECVs and evolve European ocean observing</p>
<p>This milestone is essential to achieving this SO by providing a forum for the Sister projects working on EOv-based ocean indicators to identify synergies and address common challenges in developing Ocean Indicators, as well as align their efforts with international efforts made at the GOOS level.</p>	
SO2	<p>To advance the use of EOv and ECVs for improved ESM and reduced uncertainty in projections</p>
<p>This milestone supports the development of EOv and ECVs, enhancing the work in WP4 and WP5. Stronger and more solid EOv/ECV will support the use of these variables for model validation.</p>	
SO3	<p>To create an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs</p>
<p>This milestone does not directly contribute to this specific objective. However, it supports the work of ObsSea4Clim and its related sister projects on specific EOv and related ocean indicators, as well as the challenges in developing these, including relevant data uncertainties.</p>	
SO4	<p>To develop best practices and standards for interoperable in-situ and satellite observing</p>

This milestone contributes to this SO by supporting the work across sister projects on EOVS-based ocean indicators as part of harmonisation and a unifying framework for ocean observing.

SO5

To place Europe at the forefront of the global coordination of the broader ocean-climate nexus

This milestone is linked and builds on ObsSea4Clim D2.5, D3.1 and D3.3 Deliverables. In addition, this milestone directly supports and enhances the results and work carried out in the framework of D6.2, D6.1, D6.3 and is key to achieving D6.4 and D6.6. An overview of [these deliverables](#) is available on the ObsSea4Clim website.

4. References

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